

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS ON THE DEGRADATION PRODUCTS OF BILE-ACIDS, SEX HORMONES ETC.

PART I. A SYNTHESIS OF 7-METHYL-0:3:3-BICYCLOOCTANE-1-ONE.

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A synthesis of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one by the cyclisation of ethyl 1-methyl-1-carbethoxy-cyclopentane-2-β-propionate has been described. The fused carbon ring, thus formed, is found to be mainly *trans*-.

By the oxidation of desoxycholic acid Wieland and co-workers (Wieland and Schlichting, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 276; Wieland and Vocke, *ibid.*, 1928, 177, 68) obtained a tetrabasic acid C₁₆H₂₄O₄. Its thermal decomposition resulted in the formation of a pyroketo-dicarboxylic acid C₁₅H₂₂O₅ (I) which is now regarded as a 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one derivative, on the basis of the new constitution assigned to the cholane skeleton (Wieland and Dane, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, 216, 91).

In a previous paper (Mitter and Banerjee, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 456) an investigation on the synthesis of the above type of compound has been described. As a preliminary to the synthesis of the pyroketo-dicarboxylic acid (I), a method for the synthetical preparation of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (II) has been dealt with in the present communication. A preparation of a 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-2-one has been described by Linstead and Errington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 666) in which a rigid proof regarding the position of the keto group is wanting.

Ethyl cyanoacetate has been condensed with ethyl levulate in presence of acetamide according to the method of Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327), and an excellent yield of ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl-Δ¹-butene-1:4-dicarboxylate (VI) is obtained. Addition of potassium cyanide to the above unsaturated cyano-ester is carried out according to the method of Hope and Sheldon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223). The resulting dicyano-

crystallisations from water melts at 126-27°. Both the *cis*-form (m.p. 110°) and the *trans*-form (m.p. 139°) of the above acid have been synthetically prepared by Linstead and Errington (*loc. cit.*), and they have shown the *cis*-acid to be identical with the acid obtained from 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane. But the acid obtained in our case seems to be mainly the *trans*-isomeride. The low yield of (VII) also lends support to the same conclusion. A similar mixture of stereoisomerides of acid (VIII, R=CO₂H; R'=CH₂·CO₂H) of m.p. 126° consisting mainly of the *trans*-form was obtained by Barrett, Cook and Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1065), when they prepared the reference compound. It has, however, been pointed out at a later stage that the acid which was described as melting at 126°, was, on repeated crystallisation from water found to melt at 132-133°; the mixed-melting point of the latter with the acid of m.p. 139° was 136°. For want of sufficient material, however, further crystallisation of the acid, now prepared, could not be carried out. The b.p. of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctanone obtained by Linstead and the m.p. of its semicarbazone are 80°/12 mm. and 178° respectively, whereas the b.p. of 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one and the m.p. of its semicarbazone are 70°/6 mm. and 210° respectively.

It is interesting to note that the stabilisation of the *trans*-form in the fused cyclopentano-cyclopentane system due to the presence of the angular methyl group (which according to Hückel should exhibit a moderate degree of strain) is also exhibited by the pyroketo-dicarboxylic acid (I) which, as has already been mentioned, is formed by the thermal decomposition of the acid C₁₆H₂₄O₈. Wieland has proved the stereoisomeric constitution of (I) by showing its oxidation product to be identical with the *trans*-form of the C₁₃H₂₀O₆ acid, the *cis*-form of which was prepared by the same worker by conversion of the *trans*-acid to the *cis*-anhydride followed by treating the anhydride with warm water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl-Δ¹-butene-1:4-dicarboxylate (VI).—A mixture of ethyl levulante (53.5 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (40 g.), acetamide (8 g.) and glacial acetic acid (85 c.c.) was slowly distilled from a Claisen's flask provided with a fractionating column, the temperature of the distilling vapours being kept between 105-115°. In course of about 7 hours, 86 c.c. of the distillate were collected. The residue in the flask was taken up in ether and washed several times with water. After the removal of the ether the product was fractionated. Almost the whole of the unreacted keto-ester and cyanoacetic ester, which were collected in the lower boiling

fraction, were used in subsequent lots. The unsaturated cyano-ester (55 g.) distilled at 154-160°/5.5 mm. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{12}H_{17}O_4N$ requires N, 5.85 per cent).

Diethyl 1:2-dicyano-2-methyladipate (V).—Potassium cyanide (17.5 g.) dissolved in water (95 c.c.) was slowly added with constant shaking to a solution of ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl- Δ^1 -butene-1:4-dicarboxylate (32 g.) in alcohol (152 c.c.) and water (8 c.c.). The above mixture was cooled in ice and with shaking a cooled solution of hydrochloric acid (21.3 c.c. *d* 1.15) and water (15 c.c.) (equivalent to three-fourth of the quantity of potassium cyanide added), were slowly added. The resulting slightly opaque solution was left at the room temperature for about 20-25 minutes and then acidified by pouring into a large volume of a very dilute hydrochloric acid, when a heavy oil separated. The oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate, ether removed and diethyl 1:2-dicyano-2-methyl-adipate collected at 190-192°/6 mm., yield 80-90%. (Found: N, 10.6. $C_{13}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.5 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Methyl-2-carbethoxyadipate (IV).—The above dicyano-ester (60 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8 times its volume of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 12 hours. The resulting clear solution after saturation with common salt, was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over freshly ignited sodium sulphate and the crude gummy acid (29 g.), obtained after the removal of ether, was esterified by refluxing with a solution of alcoholic sulphuric acid (300 c.c. absolute alcohol and 50 c.c. sulphuric acid, *d* 1.84), for 36 hours on a water-bath. The ester was isolated in the usual manner and distilled at 169-170°/10 mm., yield 31 g. (Found: C, 58.5; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 58.3; H, 8.3 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methyl-cyclopentanone-2:3-dicarboxylate (III).—The tricarboxylic ester (IV) in sodium-dried benzene (100 c.c.) was refluxed with powdered sodium (4.6 g) on the water-bath for 3-4 hours until all the sodium went into solution. The cooled benzene solution was acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated after dilution with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. The mixture of benzene and ether was removed. The residual oil, which gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, boiled at 153°/8.5 mm., yield 22 g. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 7.1. $C_{12}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 59.5; H, 7.4 per cent).

Ethyl 2:3-Dicarbethoxy-3-methyl-cyclopentanone-2- β -propionate [III], R=R'=CO₂Et, R''=(CH₂)₂CO₂Et.—To the sodio derivative of the

above β -ketonic ester, prepared by allowing a mixture of pulverised sodium (2.9 g.) suspended in dry benzene (100 c.c.) and 2:3-dicarboxy-3-methyl-cyclopentanone (30 g.) to stand overnight, ethyl β -chloropropionate (18 g.) was added and the whole was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hours. Water was added to the cooled reaction mixture, the benzene layer separated, washed with water and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue distilled at 194-97°/7 mm., yield 31 g. The ketonic ester does not respond to ferric chloride reaction. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 7.5. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 59.6; H, 7.6 per cent). The potassium salt of the β -ketonic ester on condensation with ethyl β -chloropropionate in xylene solution, yielded the condensation product in poor yield.

3-Carboxy-3-methyl-cyclopentanone-2- β -propionic Acid [III, R=H; R'=CO₂H; R''=(CH₂)₂CO₂H].—The above ester (13.5 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) for 36 hours. The acid solution was extracted with ether and the oily residue left after the removal of ether solidified on being kept in a vacuum desiccator. On crystallisation from ether it separated in prismatic needles, m.p. 116°, yield 8.9 g. (Found: C, 55.6; H, 6.6; Equiv., 105.3. $C_{10}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 56.07; H, 6.5 per cent. Equiv., 107).

The *semicarbazone* of the above keto-acid, on crystallisation from dilute alcohol, melted at 228°. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{11}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Methyl-1-carbethoxycyclopentane-2- β -propionate (VIII, R=CO₂Et; R'=CH₂·CH₂·CO₂Et).—A mixture of amalgamated zinc (50 g.), the above keto-acid (18 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (d 1.18, 200 c.c.) was refluxed for 12 hours, 100 c.c. more of concentrated hydrochloric acid were then added and the heating under reflux continued for another 12 hours. After cooling, the acid solution was repeatedly extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, a syrupy liquid was left as a residue which, however, showed no tendency to crystallise. The crude liquid acid (about 10 g.) was dried in a vacuum desiccator and esterified by refluxing with absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 5 c.c.) for 24 hours. The dibasic ester on being worked up in the usual manner boiled at 140-142°/4.5-5 mm., yield about 10 g. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 9.1. $C_{14}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 65.6; H, 9.4 per cent).

7-Methyl-2-carboxy-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (VII).—The above dicarboxylic ester (10 g.) was refluxed with sodium dust (1.8 g.), suspended in dry benzene (25 c.c.), for 5 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene

layer was separated and treated in the usual manner. On removal of benzene 7-methyl-2-carbethoxy-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (2.5 g.) distilled at 119-120°/6 mm., leaving some undistillable residue in the flask. The above ester gives a characteristic violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 8.5. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one (II).—The keto-ester (VII, 2.4 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing for 16 hours with an excess of 20% sulphuric acid. The resulting product was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer was washed with sodium carbonate solution and then with water, dried and the ether removed. On distillation 7-methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one was obtained as a colourless oil with strong camphoraceous smell, b.p. 70°/6 mm. (Found: C, 77.7; H, 10.06. $C_9H_{14}O$ requires C, 78.2; H, 10.1 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 21.7. $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 21.5 per cent).

Oxidation of 7-Methyl-0:3:3-bicyclooctane-1-one.—The ketone (II) (0.7 g.) was heated on the water-bath with concentrated nitric acid (4 c.c.) for 2 hours and then on the free flame for 7 hours with the addition of 4 c.c. of water. The clear solution was concentrated by keeping it in a vacuum desiccator over caustic potash when crystals of the dibasic acid separated, m.p. 123° with previous shrinking at 120°. After two crystallisations from water it had m.p. 126-27°. (Found: C, 58.06; H, 7.53. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.07; H, 7.53 per cent).

My thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for valuable advice and encouragement during the course of this work. My thanks are also due to Mr. N. Ghosh and Mr. B. Bhattacharyya for carrying out the microanalysis of some of the compounds.

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Received April 10, 1940.